

STACY Critical Experiments to Clarify the Criticality Characteristics of Non-uniform Fuel Debris Containing Concrete

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ABSTRACT

In decommissioning work of nuclear reactors that have suffered core meltdown accidents, it is important to understand the criticality characteristics of fuel debris from the viewpoint of ensuring the safety of workers. However, the composition, properties, and neutron moderation conditions of fuel debris are generally uncertain. Particularly, it is known that nonuniform composition significantly changes the criticality characteristics of fuel debris. In this study, to investigate how the criticality characteristics change due to the nonuniformity of the fuel debris composition, critical experiments were conducted simulating fuel debris containing a mixture of UO₂ fuel, water, and concrete in the critical assembly STACY. For these criticality experiments, rod-shaped concrete simulants were prepared. A uniformly arranged core and two non-uniformly arranged cores with different criticality characteristics were constructed, and the critical water levels were measured. We also conducted experimental analysis to evaluate how non-uniformity affects the critical characteristics. As a result of the evaluation, which included a comparison of neutron spectra and reaction rates, it was demonstrated that the absorption reaction rate varies due to differences in local neutron moderation ratios, which may cause changes in the criticality characteristics. This research result will contribute to the safe handling of fuel debris from the perspective of nuclear criticality safety.

Keywords: Modified STACY, Critical Experiments, Fuel Debris, Criticality Safety, Non-uniformity

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many challenges surrounding the decommissioning of Tokyo Electric Power Company (TEPC) Holdings' Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant (FDNPS). Among these, fuel debris is considered to be a source of potential risks, including the risk of criticality [1]. Therefore, there is a need to quickly evaluate the criticality of fuel debris. However, as its composition and properties are still uncertain, efforts are being made to create a database of the criticality characteristics of fuel debris through a wide range of parameter surveys using computational analysis [2]. This database also includes results from Solomon [3], which can handle the random compositions of fuel debris. However, since the validity of calculations for the composition of such fuel debris has not been confirmed, JAEA modified the Static Experiment Critical Facility (STACY) from a solution fuel system to a light water moderator system, made some samples to simulate fuel debris, and conducted critical experiments. STACY is located at the JAEA's Nuclear Science Research Institute in Tokai-mura, and it achieved its first criticality in 2024 [4].

In the accident at the FDNPS, it seemed that fuel debris that melted inside the reactor pressure vessel fell into the primary containment vessel (PCV), damaging the reinforced concrete that makes up the PCV and generating molten core-concrete interaction (MCCI) products. In fact, it has been confirmed that there is reinforced concrete in Unit 1 of FDNPS where only the rebar remains [5]. In the criticality assessment of fuel debris, it is important to evaluate the non-uniformity of the composition of the fuel debris generated by such a process. It is known that even if the same amount of components is

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contained, the effective multiplication factor can change significantly if the arrangement is uneven [6]. Here, the non-uniformity being studied includes not only structural materials such as iron and concrete that are estimated to be mixed into the fuel debris, but also light water that has entered due to the presence of voids and cracks. In the first fiscal year of the criticality experiment on fuel debris criticality characteristics using STACY, the change in the multiplication factor due to such changes in non-uniform arrangement was evaluated. In these experiments, fuel rods, water holes, and rod-shaped samples simulating reactor structural materials such as steel and concrete were prepared, and the arrangements of the loading samples were changed without changing the proportion of the samples in a specific test region. In pre-experiment analysis using the nuclear calculations that made the database, it was found that the critical water levels would change significantly due to core arrangement changes, and differences among the nuclear calculations were also confirmed. The results of these critical experiments with non-uniform configurations will be useful for validating nuclear calculations that evaluate the non-uniformity of fuel debris.

This paper describes the results of critical experiments on non-uniform arrangements of concrete, fuel, and water holes that are assumed to be included in the fuel debris, and discusses the results of the experiments and experimental analyses. Furthermore, from these considerations, the purpose is to clarify the issues regarding the handling of fuel debris with nonuniform composition.

2. EXPERIMENTS

2.1. Concrete Simulants

The way to load concrete on the STACY critical experiment was devised to prepare pellet-shaped samples to simulate concrete and seal them in metal tubes to form rod-shaped samples [7]. This is a method devised to prevent the composition of concrete, particularly the water content, from changing over time as much as possible. On the other hand, when preparing such pellet-shaped samples, consideration must be given to their homogeneity; they do not contain the irregularly shaped aggregates of various sizes that are characteristic of concrete, and their chemical composition is that of mortar. The composition of the mortar measured during sample preparation is shown in Table I. The moisture content of five randomly selected samples was 8.35 ± 0.35 wt.%. The pellets have a diameter of 0.7 cm and a stack height of approximately 142.8 cm. They are sealed in an A5052 aluminum tube (wall thickness 0.1 cm) with the same outer diameter as the STACY's fuel rod, 0.95 cm. We prepared 70 of these concrete simulants.

Table I. Composition of the mortar in the concrete simulants. [atoms·b⁻¹·cm⁻¹]

H	1.031×10^{-2}	Na	4.733×10^{-4}	Si	9.271×10^{-3}	Fe	3.744×10^{-4}
O	3.519×10^{-2}	Mg	3.917×10^{-4}	K	1.751×10^{-4}	S	9.915×10^{-5}
C	4.275×10^{-4}	Al	1.835×10^{-3}	Ca	6.314×10^{-3}		

2.2. Core Configurations

This paper describes experiments on non-uniform core arrangements consisting of fuel rods, concrete samples, and water holes. The STACY fuel is a 0.82 cm diameter UO₂ fuel with ²³⁵U enrichment of 4.98 wt.%, and has a 0.95 cm diameter Zircaloy 4 cladding tube [8]. The fuels and the concrete simulants described in section 2.1 are arranged on a grid plate with 1.27 cm intervals. In the rectangular core arrangement constructed in this way, the central 15×15 region is designated as the test region, and the surrounding area is designated as the driver fuel region. The 225 cells in the central 15×15 test region are to be filled with one of the following elements: fuel rods, concrete simulants, or water holes. For several patterns designed to make the arrangement of this test region relatively regular, non-uniform core arrangements were generated by rearranging the 15×15 cells 600 times based on random numbers, and the effective multiplication factors were calculated under constant water level conditions using MCNP6 [9] and JENDL-4.0u [10]. From the results of these preliminary analyses, several combinations and arrangements were selected in which the non-uniform arrangement resulted in a significant

increase or decrease in the effective multiplication factor compared to the relatively uniform core arrangement before the change. This paper explains experiments for one of these cases (uniform arrangement, non-uniform arrangements with large/small k_{eff} values). These core arrangements are shown in Figure 1. These core arrangements consist of 348 fuel rods (108 in the test region and 240 in the driver fuel region), 63 concrete rods, and 54 water holes. Figure 2 shows the components of the test region when it is divided into nine 3×3 sub-regions, and the moderator to fuel volume ratio (V_m/V_f) for each. When the fuel is loaded tightly in a 1.27 cm square lattice, V_m/V_f is 1.71, which is an under-moderation condition.

Figure 1. Experimental core arrangements in STACY

Fuel: 12	Fuel: 12	Fuel: 12	Fuel: 11	Fuel: 11	Fuel: 12	Fuel: 13	Fuel: 8	Fuel: 17
Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 8	Water Hole: 7	Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 9	Water Hole: 4	Water Hole: 4
Concerte: 7	Concerte: 7	Concerte: 7	Concerte: 6	Concerte: 7	Concerte: 7	Concerte: 5	Concerte: 13	Concerte: 4
Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.87	Local V_m/V_f : 4.74	Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.12	Local V_m/V_f : 6.02	Local V_m/V_f : 2.83
Fuel: 12	Fuel: 12	Fuel: 12	Fuel: 11	Fuel: 13	Fuel: 13	Fuel: 11	Fuel: 8	Fuel: 13
Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 9	Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 3	Water Hole: 9	Water Hole: 8	Water Hole: 5
Concerte: 7	Concerte: 7	Concerte: 7	Concerte: 5	Concerte: 6	Concerte: 9	Concerte: 5	Concerte: 9	Concerte: 7
Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.99	Local V_m/V_f : 3.91	Local V_m/V_f : 3.60	Local V_m/V_f : 4.99	Local V_m/V_f : 6.69	Local V_m/V_f : 3.81
Fuel: 12	Fuel: 12	Fuel: 12	Fuel: 15	Fuel: 9	Fuel: 13	Fuel: 15	Fuel: 14	Fuel: 9
Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 6	Water Hole: 3	Water Hole: 9	Water Hole: 3	Water Hole: 4	Water Hole: 3	Water Hole: 9
Concerte: 7	Concerte: 9	Concerte: 6	Concerte: 8	Concerte: 7				
Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 4.24	Local V_m/V_f : 3.12	Local V_m/V_f : 6.10	Local V_m/V_f : 3.60	Local V_m/V_f : 3.21	Local V_m/V_f : 3.34	Local V_m/V_f : 6.10

Uniform (R767)

Non-uniform (R768)

Non-uniform (R764)

Figure 2. Components and local neutron ratios in each sub-region of the test regions

2.3. Experimental Measures

The critical experiments with the non-uniform arrangements of concrete samples were conducted in late February 2025. STACY does not have any control rods, and the size of the core that will reach criticality is determined by just adjusting the water level without completely submerging the fuel rods. In normal STACY criticality experiments, including this case, the critical water level is measured at several watts thermal power after approaching criticality, and then the power is adjusted to around 0.3 to 1 watts, and the critical water level is measured again. Table II shows the critical water levels and moderator temperatures measured in this way, as well as the average critical water levels and temperatures. The critical water levels were measured by a servo-manometer water level gauge with a nominal accuracy of ± 1.5 mm. On the other hand, the water temperatures were measured using two platinum resistance thermometers with a measurement accuracy of $\pm 0.15^\circ\text{C}$, installed at the same height at the bottom of the core tank. As shown in Table II, the experiments confirmed that the critical water levels change by approximately 230 mm by just changing the arrangements of the test region. Such a large change in core sizes also leads to a large change in the water level reactivity coefficients, which

were evaluated by doubling time measurements at a slightly super-critical state to be approximately 1.3 cents/mm for R767, 1.5 cents/mm for R768, and 0.6 cents/mm for R764. In a critical assembly like STACY, the reactor's criticality is adjusted solely by adjusting the water level. This changes the effective core size, and the inverse of the water level is proportional to the geometric buckling. In other words, when the water level is low, the geometric buckling change ratio per water level change is larger than when the water level is high, and the neutron leakage also changes significantly. This is why such differences in the water level reactivity coefficient appear.

Table II. Experimental results.

Uniformity	Uniform	Non-uniform	Non-uniform
Operation Date (mm/dd/yy)	02/27/25	02/28/25	02/25/25
Run Number	R767	R768	R764
Critical Water Level (mm)	780.50	721.34	949.85
	781.58	722.33	950.54
	<i>Ave.</i> 781.04	<i>Ave.</i> 721.84	<i>Ave.</i> 950.20
Moderator Temperature (°C)	19.70	19.85	18.85
	19.65	19.85	18.85
	<i>Ave.</i> 19.68	<i>Ave.</i> 19.85	<i>Ave.</i> 18.85

3. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

In this section, we present the results of the computational experimental analysis. All results presented in this paper are based on the MCNP6 code, and the evaluated nuclear data were JENDL-5 (upd-16; J5u16) [11] and JENDL-4.0u (J40u) processed by FRENDDY-2 [12].

3.1. Effective Multiplication Factors

First, the analytical results of the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) are shown. The calculation model includes rod-shaped samples (fuel and concrete), aluminum alloy grid plates and base plates, Zircaloy-4 safety plate guide pins, a light water reflector/moderator, and a stainless steel core tank. The light water levels for each core arrangement were determined using the average critical water levels shown in Table II, and the densities of the light water were adjusted to the average temperatures. The calculations were performed using 30,000 histories per generation with 10,000 active batches after 200 inactive batches, with a statistical error of $1 \sigma < 5$ pcm.

The analysis results are shown in Figure 3. Previous research [13] has shown that analysis results for light water-moderated systems using thermal neutron scattering law (TSL) data for light water show differences of approximately 300 pcm between J40 and J5u16, and this trend appears in this result. Considering the statistical errors, the results of J40 showed little variation even when the core arrangements were changed. On the other hand, the results for J5u16 showed significant differences of up to 45 pcm in k_{eff} values between non-uniform arrangements that have large/small reactivities. Therefore, the differences between J40 and J5u16 also vary between 301 and 351 pcm due to changes in the core arrangement.

Figure 3. Computation results of k_{eff} values for the experimental analysis.

3.2. Neutron Flux Densities

In this subsection and the next, we organize the neutronic results obtained from computational analysis to explore the reasons why non-uniform configurations change the criticality characteristics.

First, the neutron spectra of the test regions were compared.

Figure 4 shows the neutron spectra of the test region average, and Figure 5 shows the neutron spectrum of the 3×3 sub-region in the center of the test region. Both figures show there are two peaks in the fast neutron energy and thermal neutron energy regions.

Figure 4 shows that the spectra evaluated using the two nuclear data sets for the three core arrangements are almost identical. There are trends that the fast energy peak becomes slightly larger and the thermal energy peak becomes slightly smaller according to the order of increasing criticality (R768 > R767 > R764).

Figure 4. Neutron spectra of whole test regions (15×15).

Figure 5. Neutron spectra of the central sub-regions (3x3).

Next, we compared the central 3x3 spectra shown in Figure 5. These spectra differ from the test region average spectra shown in

Figure 4 by two peak heights. In R768, the peak of fast energy is higher than the thermal energy, while in R764, the peak of thermal energy is higher. As shown in Figure 2, the V_m/V_f value in the center of R768 is small, while that of R764 is large. This difference in the neutron moderation conditions leads to a difference in the hardness of the spectra. The number of fuel rods loaded in the central 3x3 region differs by five between R768 and R764, and there is a possibility that nuclear fission may have contributed to these spectra, but this cannot be determined from Figure 5 alone.

3.3. Neutron Reaction Balances

To investigate other factors not identified by the comparison of neutron spectra, neutron reaction rate distributions were compared for each of the nine 3x3 subregions of the test regions. The comparisons were the nuclear fission reaction of UO_2 fuel (F.F.), the absorption reaction of UO_2 fuel (F.A.), the absorption reaction of concrete (mortar) (C.A.), and the absorption reaction of light water moderator (W.A.). The calculation results obtained using J5u16 are shown in

Figure 6. Comparing the results for the central 3x3 subregions where the neutron spectra are shown in Figure 5, it was found that the fission rate tends to increase as the values of V_m/V_f increase. Since each absorption reaction also increases as the value of V_m/V_f increases, it was presumed that the presence of a central local region with large moderation ability (large V_m/V_f) increases the absorption reactions, which causes differences in the shapes of the neutron spectra and the criticality characteristics of the core arrangements.

F. F.	8.18E-07	F. F.	9.68E-07	F. F.	8.22E-07
F. A.	9.34E-07	F. A.	1.07E-06	F. A.	9.47E-07
C. A.	1.62E-08	C. A.	1.90E-08	C. A.	1.63E-08
W. A.	1.91E-08	W. A.	2.26E-08	W. A.	1.92E-08
V_m/V_f	4.24	V_m/V_f	4.24	V_m/V_f	4.24
F. F.	9.67E-07	F. F.	1.15E-06	F. F.	9.69E-07
F. A.	1.07E-06	F. A.	1.21E-06	F. A.	1.09E-06
C. A.	1.90E-08	C. A.	2.24E-08	C. A.	1.90E-08
W. A.	2.25E-08	W. A.	2.69E-08	W. A.	2.26E-08
V_m/V_f	4.24	V_m/V_f	4.24	V_m/V_f	4.24
F. F.	8.21E-07	F. F.	9.69E-07	F. F.	8.18E-07
F. A.	9.42E-07	F. A.	1.08E-06	F. A.	9.56E-07
C. A.	1.62E-08	C. A.	1.90E-08	C. A.	1.62E-08
W. A.	1.91E-08	W. A.	2.26E-08	W. A.	1.91E-08
V_m/V_f	4.24	V_m/V_f	4.24	V_m/V_f	4.24

Uniform (R767)

F. F.	8.71E-07	F. F.	1.02E-06	F. F.	7.73E-07
F. A.	9.97E-07	F. A.	1.09E-06	F. A.	9.14E-07
C. A.	1.72E-08	C. A.	1.99E-08	C. A.	1.55E-08
W. A.	2.03E-08	W. A.	2.37E-08	W. A.	1.80E-08
V_m/V_f	4.87	V_m/V_f	4.74	V_m/V_f	4.24
F. F.	9.99E-07	F. F.	1.05E-06	F. F.	7.84E-07
F. A.	1.13E-06	F. A.	1.16E-06	F. A.	9.54E-07
C. A.	1.96E-08	C. A.	2.07E-08	C. A.	1.59E-08
W. A.	2.33E-08	W. A.	2.44E-08	W. A.	1.83E-08
V_m/V_f	4.99	V_m/V_f	3.91	V_m/V_f	3.60
F. F.	6.87E-07	F. F.	1.05E-06	F. F.	6.75E-07
F. A.	8.32E-07	F. A.	1.17E-06	F. A.	8.37E-07
C. A.	1.40E-08	C. A.	2.04E-08	C. A.	1.37E-08
W. A.	1.60E-08	W. A.	2.45E-08	W. A.	1.57E-08
V_m/V_f	3.12	V_m/V_f	6.10	V_m/V_f	3.60

Non-uniform (R768)

F. F.	8.88E-07	F. F.	1.16E-06	F. F.	6.29E-07
F. A.	9.64E-07	F. A.	1.17E-06	F. A.	8.03E-07
C. A.	1.75E-08	C. A.	2.19E-08	C. A.	1.32E-08
W. A.	2.07E-08	W. A.	2.69E-08	W. A.	1.47E-08
V_m/V_f	4.12	V_m/V_f	6.02	V_m/V_f	2.83
F. F.	1.23E-06	F. F.	1.48E-06	F. F.	9.84E-07
F. A.	1.19E-06	F. A.	1.37E-06	F. A.	1.05E-06
C. A.	2.35E-08	C. A.	2.77E-08	C. A.	1.93E-08
W. A.	2.87E-08	W. A.	3.45E-08	W. A.	2.29E-08
V_m/V_f	4.99	V_m/V_f	6.69	V_m/V_f	3.81
F. F.	7.20E-07	F. F.	9.23E-07	F. F.	1.02E-06
F. A.	8.48E-07	F. A.	9.88E-07	F. A.	1.08E-06
C. A.	1.46E-08	C. A.	1.82E-08	C. A.	1.95E-08
W. A.	1.68E-08	W. A.	2.15E-08	W. A.	2.37E-08
V_m/V_f	3.21	V_m/V_f	3.34	V_m/V_f	6.10

Non-uniform (R764)

Figure 6. Reaction rate distributions on each sub-region (J5u16).

3.4. Discussions

From the above results, it was found that the change in criticality characteristics due to the non-uniform arrangement, including concrete and water holes, is largely due to the difference in absorption reactions caused by the difference in local neutron moderation conditions. When calculating the effective multiplication factor for R768 and R764, which were conducted in this study, at the same water level, the difference in the effective multiplication factors is nearly 2.5 dollars (more than 1,700 pcm). Furthermore, the changes in k_{eff} values from R767, which has a relatively uniform arrangement, were approximately +560 to -1160 pcm. This fact shows that the criticality may be higher due to the effect of non-uniformity than when evaluated under uniform conditions. These differences are extremely large compared to the uncertainty in the results of computations, such as the approximately 350 pcm difference between J5u16 and J40u obtained by experimental analysis, and the variation of around 50 pcm observed in J5u16 due to differences in the core arrangements. Therefore, when managing nuclear criticality safety for fuel debris with non-uniform compositions, it is necessary to decide on a methodology that takes into account the fact that non-uniformity can cause large nuclear uncertainties.

4. CONCLUSIONS

To clarify the effect of non-uniformity on the critical characteristics of fuel debris containing concrete, critical experiments were carried out using the STACY critical assembly. The difference in criticality characteristics due to non-uniformity obtained in the preliminary analysis for planning the experiments was confirmed by experiments with actual non-uniform core arrangements. Investigations of the neutron spectra and reaction rate distributions at the test regions in the non-uniform arrangements revealed that the criticality characteristics of the non-uniform arrangements would be characterized by the presence of local sub-regions with high neutron moderation ratios in the test regions, which increase the neutron absorption reaction rates in those sub-regions. Furthermore, since the change in the multiplication factor due to non-uniformity in the computational analysis was significantly larger than the effects of uncertainties due to differences in nuclear data, it is concluded that sufficient consideration must be given to non-uniformity when managing the criticality safety of fuel debris.

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